

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

What are Knowledge Technologies?

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable, first submitted in M12 as v1, provides a conceptual overview of some of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy from an institutional perspective. Module D focuses on the use of personal data and user profiling. Module E focuses on the control of individual speech and action. This version builds on v2 to begin to provide a toolkit to advance the state of the art in these two domains.

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1.1 What are Knowledge Technologies?

Knowledge technologies, as distinct from information technologies, have been defined in the Module C of the social risk toolkit. Within KT4D, knowledge technologies are thus defined as technologies which support and contribute to the creation and dissemination of knowledge.

Rather than conceptualise the notion of knowledge technologies under a personal data and user profiling lens, this section will build upon this existing definition and define the terms ‘personal data’ and ‘user profiling’ in sections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2 respectively. Beginning with a brief history of the terms, each section will outline some common uses of personal data and user profiling.

1.1.1 Personal Data

Personal data, as defined by the European Commission (2018), “is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual”. This can include but is of course not limited to, names, addresses, special category data, biometric and genetic data, and health data.

To better understand the importance of personal data, we must understand its place in the data ecosystem. Drawing on the distinction made in Module C between knowledge and information, data leads to information when it is organised and interpreted. With an ever-expanding range of technologies that monitor, generate, and collect data about us, both the data and the technology that does this have intersected almost all aspects of our lives, including civic participation.

If data is collected from us and about us, then the question arises as to who *owns* personal data. The debate seems to converge on the idea that data subjects are the default data owners (Al-Khouri, 2012; Hummel, et al., 2021; Black, 2021; Zang, 2023). The strength of this ownership and the rights it confers however is hotly debated (Hummel, et al., 2021).¹ Regardless of ownership data, for better or for worse, has become redefined in the technology space as a kind of currency in the digital age (Schwartz, 2003: 2056). Data, and by extension personal data, has therefore typically been understood as valuable almost exclusively in a financial, or commodity, sense. There is an emerging countertrend however to understand data as a public good. Drawing on information economists such as Stiglitz (1999) and Varian (1999), Taylor (2016: 2) notes that data is a public good if we see it as ‘non-rivalrous’ and ‘non-excludable’. The concept of big data however creates a system where data becomes ‘functionally excludable’ because of the value the private sector gains by controlling it (Taylor, 2016: 2).

‘Small data’ (our individual personal data) becomes big data when aggregated into larger datasets (Lupton, 2018: 1). Whilst we often understand big data in terms of the anonymous datasets that institutions and corporations collect and utilise, Lupton (2018: 2) introduces the idea of ‘personal big data’ to understand the experiences and sense-making of people navigating the way their data is

¹ For an in-depth discussion of the varying views of data ownership see Hummel, Braun and Dabrock (2021) who systemise these views under four themes: the modes that can be used to control data; commodification of data; protection of data versus data as a tool for the common good; and individual versus collective claims of data as property.

collected and used. In particular the collection of data from social media has made it incredibly easy to gather information about people. For example, studies have shown that by merely looking at likes on Facebook, algorithms can correctly predict the political affiliation of individuals 85% of the time (Tufekci, 2017). This has ramifications in the political context. We cannot simply unplug and disengage, and so the inevitable effects of the use of our personal data need to be understood, mitigated, or changed if we are to navigate this merging of knowledge technologies and data into our everyday lives.

1.1.2 User Profiling

Coupling personal data with information about user preferences, interests, and behaviours has created the opportunity to develop profiles of types of users, or more recently *specific* users, based on certain metrics.² User profiling can therefore be described as the process of generating data-driven descriptions or “virtual representations” of individuals (Cufoglu, 2014: 1). The data that makes up a user profile may differ in each use case, however it is typically a mix of data that has been explicitly given by the user (for example, when signing up to a social media site you may give your name, age, and location), or may be ‘learnt’ or predicted based on user behaviour. User profiles are used in a variety of domains that span all aspects of our digital lives, such as social media, online news outlets, and our calendar management systems (Schiaffino and Amandi, 2009: 193). User profiling techniques present a unique opportunity for governments, institutions, and private organisations to correlate data about both groups of people, and specific individuals (Hildebrandt, 2008b: 303).

Hildebrandt (2008a: 26) argues for an understanding of profiling from a knowledge generation perspective. We may for example want to understand profiling as a way to generate “discovery-driven”, or data-driven, hypotheses which can then be tested once the profiles are applied to specific contexts (Hildebrandt, 2008a: 18-19). Some questions then arise as to who is using these profiles, in what ways they are used, and the effects accuracy, and inaccuracy, of these profiles can have on democracy.

One such use of user profiling is in recommender systems. The ways we want to be able to access information online have increasingly become more individualistic. As such, recommender systems have become increasingly individualised to cater to our want of personalised information – something that is possible given the sheer amount of data available (Eke, et al., 2019: 144907). Recommender systems in part rely on user profiling to recommend content to us and reduce the time we spend searching for information (Roy & Dutta, 2022: 1-3).

1.2.3 Automated Decision-Making

Automated decision-making (ADM) is perhaps the most common thematic under which the effects of AI on democracy have been discussed. AI systems can assist or replace human decision-makers in various domains, such as public administration, health care, education and justice. While these

² For example, the shift on social media platforms to hyper-personalised feeds.

systems may offer benefits such as efficiency, accuracy, and consistency of decisions, they also pose significant challenges for democratic values and institutions. These challenges include the lack of transparency, accountability and participation in the design of AI systems as well as the potential for algorithmic bias and discrimination. The ethical and social implications of delegating human agency to machines is a further issue. This deliverable will in part focus on conceptualising the challenges that ADM poses, particularly from the use of user profiling within ADM systems.

1.2 The Value of Democracy

There are both instrumental and intrinsic reasons to value democracy. In short, democracy is valuable instrumentally because (1) democracy can assist us in producing laws and policies that protect the rights and interests of citizens, (2) democracy more often than other systems produces the right laws and policies (there are epistemic benefits to democratic decision-making), and (3) democracy can improve the people in it through increased autonomy and knowledge (Christiano and Bajaj, 2022). Intrinsic reasons to value democracy include self-governance and liberty, the value of public justification and deliberation, and the promotion of equality. We take each of these valuable aspects in turn.

Concerning the instrumental value of democracy, other governmental structures, for example oligarchy or dictatorships, do not protect the rights and interests of citizens as well. Landmore (2013: 3) for example argues that “a democratic decision procedure is likely to be a better decision procedure than any non-democratic decision procedures, such as a council of experts or a benevolent dictator” because of the epistemic benefits gained from civic participation and democratic deliberation. There are also strong correlations to be found between democracies and the protection of core rights (Landman, 2018).

One way to conceptualise these epistemic benefits include Condorcet’s Jury Theorem (Condorcet, 1785).³ Other ways to understand the epistemic benefits of democracy include the notion of cognitive diversity (Waldron, 1995), the idea that diversity can trump ability (Landmore, 2013; Hong and Page, 2004), and the fact that the citizens within democracies may be better placed to understand and identify problems in society, even if experts may be needed to devise the best solution (Dewey and Rogers, 2012). Condorcet’s Jury Theorem suggests that if we assume that voters are competent, sincere, and statistically independent of each other, then the probability of the right decision being made increases the more voters there are. These conditions however are not always met. For example, voters may lack independence (Anderson, 2008: 133; Estlund, 2008), or importantly in the context of knowledge technologies, AI and big data, some groups may have better or different access to information than others. Finally, we may instrumentally value democracy because of the autonomy and active decision-making role it confers to its citizens. Concerning intrinsic reasons to value democracy, we may value democracy because it ensures citizens have the ability to self-govern (Gould, 1988), the laws democracies make are publicly justified (Habermas, 1996), and it protects and promotes equality amongst its citizens.

³ For more on Condorcet’s Jury Theorem see Barry (1965), Cohen (1986), Grofman and Feld (1988), and Goodin and Spiekerman (2019).

There are of course multiple forms and degrees of democracy which offer varying levels of freedom to their citizens. This section has only sought to discuss the benefits of democracy if it were employed in an ideal setting. In reality increasing political polarisation and the erosion of the power of elected representatives may see some democracies move closer to illiberal ones. This is of particular importance to KT4D as the use of knowledge technologies may differ and produce different outcomes under varying levels of citizen freedom. Later versions of this Module, and the social risk toolkit as a whole, will explore the implications of the use of knowledge technologies in different democratic contexts.

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